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TES INTEGRATION FOR HEAT-TO-COLD SOLUTIONS: COMPARISON OF MODELLING APPROACHES FOR A CASE STUDY IN A BIOFUELS PLANT IN GREECE

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ABSTRACT

The present paper compares three modelling approaches (developed by the authors) aiming to the sizing of Thermal Energy Storage solutions coupled to an absorption cooling system in the MIL OIL biofuels plant in Central Macedonia, Greece, aiming to meet the cooling needs of the biodiesel production line and the digester. The three modelling approaches had all the goal of sizing the TES to properly cover the local demand and maximise the local waste heat exploitation, however results are not fully aligned each other, showing the importance (in this type of projects) to carefully evaluate the design of the integrated plant.

Keywords: thermal energy storage, hot, cold, TES, Waste heat recovery, biofuels, industry, absorption cooling

INTRODUCTION

Industrial activities account for a significant portion of global energy consumption, primarily due to their intensive requirements for heat, cooling, and electricity [1]. In light of growing environmental and decarbonization concerns, the development of innovative and sustainable technologies to meet industrial energy demands has become essential [2].

Among these technologies, waste heat recovery (WHR) plays a key role in improving overall energy efficiency [3]. Recovered heat can be effectively utilized not only for process heating [4] or power generation [5], but also for the production of cooling through absorption [6] and adsorption [7] refrigeration systems, as investigated in the RE-WITCH Project [8]. These thermally driven chillers transform low-grade heat into useful cooling energy, enabling trigeneration schemes (heat, power, and cooling) that enhance plant flexibility and sustainability [9].

In this context, the synergistic combination of waste heat recovery, thermal energy storage (TES), and ab-/adsorption-based cooling [10] offers a promising pathway to decarbonize industrial energy systems, improve exergy efficiency, and promote circular use of energy across multiple processes [11]. In this context, coupling TES at different temperature levels could further maximize the energy efficiency of the trigeneration solutions as analysed by different researchers. TES coupling, particularly at different temperature levels and for different purposes, has technical and economic challenges [12], thus developing specific modelling tools [13] [14] and compare their results is crucial. This work, elaborated in the framework of RE-WITCH Horizon Europe project, presents and compares three modelling approaches aiming to optimally size TES (hot or cold) coupled to an absorption cooling system powered by waste and solar heat in a biofuels plant in Northern Greece. The paper has the goal of comparing the modelling tools (highlighting pros and cons of each of them) and their results and to collect from these modelling approaches relevant insights about how to properly size TES in this type of industrial plants and for this type of trigeneration purposes.

PLANT DESCRIPTION

The MIL OIL plant is located in the industrial zone of Serres in Central Macedonia, Greece, and produces biodiesel and biogas. The produced biogas is burned in three combined heat and power (CHP) units, two with an electrical load of 1067 kW_{el} and another larger one with a power output of 1562 kW_{el}. It's worth noting that significant amounts of heat are generated from the cooling circuit and the exhaust gases of the CHP units. With all 3 CHP units operational, the hot water stream available for utilization is at a temperature level of 99-100°C, with a maximum theoretical heat recovery load of 3698 kW_{th}. The biodiesel units require both heating and cooling. Additionally, the digester, which is necessary for biogas production, has significant cooling requirements.

MIL OIL has installed an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) unit, which is fed with a hot water stream to produce electrical energy. The ORC unit is designed to be supplied with a maximum thermal load of 2390 kW_{th}, and the nominal power capacity is 150 kW_{el}. Under the RE-WITCH project, the implementation of an absorption cooling system has been proposed, which utilizes the available waste heat in the form of hot water to cover the cooling loads of the biodiesel reactors and the digester. The low-temperature (LT) cooling load is designed to be 200 kW_c with a cold water supply temperature of 10/15°C, aiming to cover the biodiesel cooling needs. The design value of the high-temperature (HT)

cooling load is 240 kW_c with a cold water supply temperature of $20/25^\circ\text{C}$. The HT cooling load regards the digester cooling load, with a nominal value of 166 kW_c , and other cooling needs of the factory, such as for the post-digester. Moreover, in the framework of the RE-WITCH project, the installation of a solar field of high-vacuum flat plate collectors with an aperture area of about 141.12 m^2 is proposed to provide additional useful heat in the form of hot water, with a peak thermal capacity of 97 kW_{th} . Notably, if the heat produced by the CHP units does not feed the ORC and the absorption chiller, the largest portion of this heat will be rejected as waste. A schematic representation of all the processes at the MIL OIL plant is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Overall schematic representation of the industrial processes, solar thermal collectors, and all the integrated systems (ORC, absorption chiller, and biodiesel units) in parallel operation at the MIL OIL plant.

As it can be seen in Fig.1, the overall plant schematics foresee integration of both hot and cold TES (sensible TES – water tank). The goal of the modelling approaches proposed by University of Genova (UNIGE), University of Birmingham (UoB) and CERTH (presented in the following chapters) is to optimally size these TES in order to properly manage the overall Waste Heat recovery and minimize plant costs (particularly looking at cooling production).

PROPOSED MODELLING APPROACHES

UNIGE WECOMP THERMOECONOMIC MODELLING APPROACH

Thermo-economics establishes a link between thermodynamic performance—particularly energy and exergy flows—and the economic behavior of an energy system. It relies on the concepts of specific consumption and energy cost of flows, forming the internal economy of the conversion process. This approach is especially valuable in poly-generative districts, where energy managers must balance thermal and electrical demands while optimizing grid exchanges. By combining component parameters (efficiency, nominal power) with local economic data (fuel and electricity prices, inflation, equipment costs), thermo-economics correlates money and energy flows, revealing where energy or cost savings are achievable. The allocation of energy costs is straightforward for conventional or renewable-based CHP units, characterized by a single energy input and output revenue. However, accurate cost tracking becomes crucial when waste heat or renewable heat is recovered to produce cooling through absorption or adsorption systems instead of conventional electric compression technologies. In this analysis, UNIGE team used the WECOMP Modelling tool [15], already used in the past for activities related to absorption solutions [16]. WECOMP is a thermo-economic modelling tool, aiming to optimize the sizing and the management of energy systems in multi-actors contexts (e.g. polygenerative districts etc.). All the energy systems present in MIILOIL plants are modeled using hourly resolution allowing assessment of optimal thermal and electric power flows also once properly managed by energy storage, via a “energy storage fictitious costs approach” already presented by the authors in polygenerative contexts also comparing the different roles of electric and thermal storages for such applications. [17]. The layout of MIILOIL plant as modelled in WECOMP tool is presented in Fig.2a.

UOB MODELLING APPROACH

Similarly to UNIGE WECOMP tool, UoB developed a techno-economic optimisation tool to assess and optimise integrated multi-energy systems. Built in Python 3.12 using Pyomo 6.8.0, it simulates the interactions among electricity, thermal, and cooling networks, including renewable sources and Thermal Energy Storage (TES). The tool minimises total operational cost by optimising the hourly dispatch of technologies and storage units. It supports linear programming and scenario-based analysis, enabling evaluation of system configurations, storage sizing, Levelized Cost of Storage (LCOS), and detailed visualisation of energy flows and component performance. Based on UoB developed optimization tool, all the energy systems are modeled using hourly resolution for a selected time period (seasonal or annual), allowing assessment of optimal energy flows, storage operation, and technology synergies under real market and climatic conditions. The architecture of the MIILOIL Demosite integrated energy system is shown in Fig. 2b. The system is designed to serve electricity, heating, and cooling demands in an industrial setting, leveraging solar thermal resources, waste heat recovery, and TES systems. The system is modeled to maintain hourly energy balances across three

domains: electricity, thermal energy, and cooling (HT, LT, or both) levels. These balances ensure that generation, storage, and conversion units collectively meet the dynamic energy demands of the industrial site. The tool develops a multi-energy system optimization model capturing interactions among conversion technologies, storage, and variable electricity, heating, and cooling demands. Implemented in Python 3.12 with Pyomo 6.8.0 and solved via Gurobi 12.0, it uses hourly resolution for realistic operation planning. The linear programming formulation minimizes total system costs while ensuring energy balance, equipment performance, and realistic storage behavior. The architecture supports scenario-based analyses, enabling flexible configurations (e.g., activating TES units or varying demands) for techno-economic assessments and optimal sizing strategies. TES is modeled as a black box via state-of-charge dynamics with charging/discharging efficiencies, excluding temperature degradation or long-term losses. Post-optimization routines compute economic indicators (e.g., LCOS) and visualize component-level performance metrics, as detailed in the "LCOS calculation" subsection.

CERTH MODELLING APPROACH

CERTH has developed MATLAB Based thermodynamic models to simulate various energy systems under dynamic conditions. First, non-concentrating solar thermal collectors have been modelled, as these systems will be integrated in the MILOIL plant. Moreover, TES tanks, which will be coupled with solar thermal collectors, thermal processes, or cooling processes, are simulated. Furthermore, the modelling of the LiBr/water absorption cooling cycle is presented. The modelling of an Organic Rankine cycle (ORC) module is also provided. All the components mass and energy balance equations have been integrated in such MATLAB models together with performance curves/maps as provided by RE-WITCH technology developers (such values have been integrated in the previous tools too). Looking at TES models, both Hot and Cold TES models are modeled through mixing zone modeling, which is a common strategy in the literature [19]. MILOIL Plant modelling via CERTH approach is presented in Fig.2c.

Fig. 2. Overall schematics of the modelling tools used by UNIGE (a), UoB (b) and CERTH (c).

RESULTS AND COMPARISON OF THE MODELLING APPROACHES

The optimal storage solutions at both hot and cold storage temperatures as provided by CERTH, UNIGE, and UoB are compared and discussed. In MILOIL Plant, considering: 1) the large amount of WH always available (3698 kW_{th}), 2) the limited heating demand of the biodiesel process production (maximum value of 319 kW_{th}, to be fully covered by the available WH with no major issues), 3) that a 440 kW_{th} Absorption chiller has been considered for the study and that cooling demand often goes beyond this amount of cold thermal power needed, UNIGE WECOMP tool has been studied mostly to size a Cold TES (cold glycole+water between 0 and 5°C – CAPEX = 80 €/kWh) to be integrated in MILOIL process. Storing excess of WH (always present) in Hot TES is not meaningful indeed, while it is meaningful to cover cold production of the ABSORPTION CHILLER to cover via the COLD TES peak moments in which the overall cooling demand is higher than 440 kW_{th}. The theoretical capacity needed (to fully cover the cooling demand via ABSORPTION CHILLER, thus not relying on the air driven compression chiller at all) is according to UNIGE calculation 6330,52 kWh_{th}. This value was calculated, imposing to cover the cooling demand via absorption solutions. As it can be imagined this solution requires significant CAPEX (506440 € only for the TES, plus 264000 € for the H2C system, plus 25000 € for the solar panels) that can be paid back via the electric bill (electricity consumed for cooling) savings (144894 €/yr) in around five years and half. However, looking at a pure cost optimization, the optimizer, sized the COLD TES up to 1365.75 kWh_{th} covering with an air-water chiller (supposed COP=3) the

“missing gaps” (around 9343 kWh_{th} of cooling per year, thus around 3115 kWh_{el}) with an annual cost of the electricity bill of 591,42 €, thus enabling savings per 144302.76 €/a. The CAPEX of this scenarios is much lower, particularly for what it concerns the TES (109260 € for a total investment of 398260 €), thus enabling a payback period lower than three years. This is mostly due to the fact that (even considering a limited cost of the cold TES – cold water tank – around 80 €/kWh), the extra cost of electricity is around 500€/yr, while a larger TES would cost around 50 k€ (instead of around 10 k€ more).

According to the analysis conducted by CERTH, the scenario with two TES tanks, one hot water tank with a capacity of 50 m³ for the biodiesel units and another cold-water tank with a capacity of 30 m³ for the cooling storage at the digester, is considered the optimal solution in terms of thermodynamics. The CERTH tool defines not only optimal storage capacities but also the positions where these storage solutions should be placed. It is important for the plant operator to identify the most advantageous locations for installing storage systems in order to enhance the overall efficiency of plant operations. Moreover, seasonal (3-month) capacities in [kWh] are determined by the UoB optimisation tool for both the hot and the cold storage systems. The capacities range from 5,559-29,717 kWh and 4,984-16,960 kWh for the hot and the cold storage unit, respectively. Based on these capacities, the determined average values of volumes are equal to 31.5 m³ and 32.7 m³ for the hot and cold-water storage tank, respectively. Furthermore, according to the tool of UNIGE, the optimized cold storage capacity is determined at 1,365.75 kWh, while the hot storage is neglected due to the continuous availability of the waste heat. Based on these calculations, an average volume of 11.9 m³ is defined for the cold-water storage tank. At this point, the CERTH tool is re-run, taking into account the storage capacities as defined by the UoB and UNIGE tools and the strategic positions inside the plant, as defined previously by the CERTH tool. The storage tank volumes, determined for the optimal cases of the UoB and UNIGE tools, are fully optimised and similar to those defined by the CERTH simulation tool. As a result, the annual cooling production amount at both the low-temperature (biodiesel), and high-temperature (digester) levels is quite similar. The optimal scenarios provided by CERTH, UNIGE, and UoB are presented comparatively in **Hata! Başvuru kaynağı bulunamadı.**

Table 4. Comparative results of optimal scenarios as provided by CERTH, UNIGE, and UoB.

Results	CERTH Optimal scenario	UNIGE Optimal scenario	UoB Optimal scenario
Hot TES (m ³)	50.0	-	31.5
Cold TES (m ³)	30.0	11.9	32.7
Digester (HT) cooling production (MWh)	1378.4	1362.9	1379.7
Coverage of digester cooling load	94.8%	93.7%	94.9%
Biodiesel (LT) cooling production (MWh)	1717.3	1717.4	1717.4
Coverage of biodiesel cooling load	98.0%	98.0%	98.0%

CONCLUSIONS

The three modelling tools showed the relevance of cold TES integration (more than hot TES) for a proper management of absorption chillers in industrial processes like MILOIL ones, aiming to maximise waste heat exploitation and the optimal operability of heat-to-cold machines. The modelling approaches showed similar results and the paper also presented how more thermodynamic oriented tools (like CERTH ones) could be more effective (once sizing TES) thanks to a proper interaction with thermoeconomic tools like UoB/UNIGE ones which can limited objective targets of TES sizing. This is exactly what RE-WITCH project aims to do, in order to properly size and manage the assets to be installed in its demotesites.

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REFERENCES

1. C. Feng, G. Pan, J. Yang, Identification of key renewable energy sectors for global energy transition based on industrial linkage analysis, *Renewable Energy*, June 2025
2. Meng, Y.; Yang, Y.; Chung, H.; Lee, P.-H.; Shao, C. Enhancing Sustainability and Energy Efficiency in Smart Factories: A Review. *Sustainability* 2018, 10, 4779. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10124779>
3. Hamid Reza Rahbari, Brian Elmegaard, Ahmad Arabkoohsar, Thermochemical technologies for industrial waste heat recovery: A comprehensive review, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, June 2025
4. J. Zhao et al., Industrial reheating furnaces: A review of energy efficiency assessments, waste heat recovery potentials, heating process characteristics and perspectives for steel industry, *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*, March 2021

5. Y. Zhao et al., A novel waste heat power generation system based on the integration of Carnot battery and waste heat recovery in a cement plant, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 2025,
6. R. Nikbakhti, Absorption cooling systems – Review of various techniques for energy performance enhancement, *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 2020
7. S. Kumar Singh et al. Recent advancements and sustainable solutions in adsorption-based cooling systems integrated with renewable energy sources and industrial waste heat: A review, *Cleaner Engineering and Technology*, December 2024
8. <https://ieecp.org/projects/re-witch/>
9. Calise, F.; Dentice D'Accadia, M. Simulation of Polygeneration Systems. *Energies* **2016**
10. Moslem Sharifishourabi, Ibrahim Dincer, Atef Mohany, A novel trigeneration energy system with two modes of operation for thermal energy storage and hydrogen production, *Energy*, 2024
11. M. M. Ismail, I Dincer et al., Assessment of a solar-powered trigeneration plant integrated with thermal energy storage using phase change materials, *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*, November 2024
12. Ma, Zhiwei & Zondag, Herbert & Sevault, Alexis & Kauko, Hanne & Vasta, Salvatore & Roskilly, Tony. (2025). Integration of thermal energy storage in industrial processes: challenges and opportunities. *Green Energy and Sustainability*. 1-11. 10.47248/ges2505010001.
13. Amedeo Ceruti et al, Integrating renewable energy and thermal storage in district heating networks: A design optimization approach, *Energy Conversion and Management*, December 2025
14. R. Kotegov et al., Multi-method optimization of solar district energy systems with battery and thermal energy storage via real-time TRNSYS-Python coupling, *Applied Energy*, December 2025
15. <https://tpg.unige.eu/w-ecomp/>
16. S. Barberis, M. Rivarolo, A. F. Massardo, Thermo-economic optimization of a real polygenerative district, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, March 2016
17. S. Barberis, M. Rivarolo, A. Traverso, A.F. Massardo, Thermo-economic analysis of the energy storage role in a real polygenerative district, *Journal of Energy Storage*, Volume 5, 2016,
18. Benvenuto, M, Barberis, S, Traverso, A, & Sciacovelli, A. "A Systematic Approach to Evaluate the Thermo-Economic Potential of Rankine-Based Carnot Batteries for Industrial Decarbonization." *Proceedings of the ASME Turbo Expo 2024: Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition*. Volume 5: Cycle Innovations. London, United Kingdom. June 24–28, 2024. V005T06A027. ASME. <https://doi.org/10.1115/GT2024-127461>
19. Evangelos Bellos and Christos Tzivanidis, "Parametric analysis and optimization of a solar driven trigeneration system based on ORC and absorption heat pump," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 161, pp. 493–509, 2017.